

A STUDY ON WOMEN'S PREFERENCE TOWARDS TWO WHEELER BRANDS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CALICUT CITY

V. Athulya* & Dr. M. Ramya**

* Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Hindusthan College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce (IB), Hindusthan College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Women now drive the world economy. Women are the world's most influential consumers, and their impact on the economy is rising every year. Customer Perception remains a research topic of strong interest. By keeping in view that future non-refundable income of average household people will increase, so in future their demand and need both increases. The study was carried out to assess the amount of women's preference towards Two Wheeler Brands. The outcome of the study was based on 200 consumers selected from Calicut City of Kerala. The data required for the study have been collected through questionnaires and analyzed by using statistical techniques as tools, such as Simple Percentage and Z test. The study pointed out that the women's preference towards two wheeler brands.

Key Words: Preference of Ladies over Two Wheeler, Brand Preference & Buying Behaviour

Introduction:

India has overtaken China to materialize the world's leading market for two-wheelers. A sum of 17.7 million two-wheelers were sold here preceding year, that's over 48,000 units every day. Indian two wheeler production is as old as 53 years. Until the middle of 80's there were only three major motorbike producers in India namely Rajdoot, Escorts and Enfield. The two-wheeler industry is perhaps mainly occurring place in terms of new models launched, upgraded products and innovative marketing techniques. Today the Indian two-wheeler markets in highly aggressive the numerous companies who offer anything and everything that a consumer demands and that too at reasonable price. The Indian two-wheeler industry is conquered by three players, Bajaj, Honda and TVS Suzuki, who account for 80 percent of the total two-wheeler market. The industry can be divided in to three broad segments: scooters, motorcycles and mopeds. In the scooters segment Bajaj in the market leader, Honda is the market leader in the motor cycles segment and in the segment of mopeds, TVS controls the major chunk of the market. Most Indian players in the two-wheeler industry had been into some kind of strategic alliance, technical collaboration or joint venture with foreign players

Review of Literature:

M. Arutselvi (2011), in her paper entitled on, "A study on customer satisfaction towards TVS Bikes" in kanchipuram town, it has examined that the performance of SARADAS Auto Agencies for retaining the customers by their approved sales. The study has used descriptive research method and has adopted survey method for data collection. A sample of 130 respondents has been occupied for this study. The study has concluded that the sales of Saradas Auto Agencies for TVS two wheelers were superior because of the right approach of the group of genuine mechanics.

Bijapurkar, Rama. (2013) Explores the field of consumerism in India and the strategies that are developed to satisfy the consumer. In this book, the author discussed about the surroundings in which consumers survive; the way they believe, their heterogeneous nature and their transformation. India being an rising market in the world, there are a lot of business opportunities. The author tries to educate the readers how to be ready to grasp these opportunities and use them. As an overall result of different changes, India is now in the third decade after liberalization. And he mentioned the structure of consumption and behavior of consumers in his book.

Vijay, Kumar M; Chandra, Basha and Chand,S. (2015) Price is arguably the most vital and important influence on the positioning of the product and its growth and hence has a direct impact on the volume of the sale of the product and share in the market. If put to the right and thoughtful use, effective pricing can earn a business organization a major and sustained share in a given market. A marketing manager can also maintain resale price of his product, maximize profit and achieve the targeted return on investment. As we know, price of any product can directly influence the demand factor and other factors of production of a product directly. Price fixation of any product is not simple and it depends upon several factors like product cost, availability of substitutes, demand, market share, and geographic factors and so on. Keeping the fixation of price of a product in view, the manufacturer has to think over the price of the product at four levels .i.e. reasonable price, high price, low price and resale value of the product

Rajesh Mahotra 2012 found that mileage and engine power are the important factors which affects the buying behaviour, while consumers are not bothered about price.

Abdul Karim B.A. 2012 observed that comfort and convenience is the driving force for the purchase of two wheeler. The study noted that over crowd is the major reason for avoiding the public transport.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the preference of ladies over two-wheeler
- ✓ To evaluate various factors, which determines the buying decision
- ✓ To suggest suitable measures based on the level of awareness of satisfaction

Research Methodology:

Both primary and secondary data were used for the present study. Convenient random sampling method has been used for this study. Secondary data have been collected from Websites, Books and Journals. Calicut town consumers are used for the study. The data required for the study have been collected through the structured questionnaire. 200 respondents were considered for the study purpose.

Tools for Analysis:

Percentage Analysis and Z test has been used in this study.

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant difference in the growth in the buying decision of two wheeler among women consumers.

Analysis and Discussion:

Table 1: Simple Percentage Analysis

Factor	Option	Respondents	Percentage
Age	Below 10	20	10
	10-20	75	37.5
	21-30	60	30
	Above 30	45	22.5
Marital Status	Single	140	70
	Married	60	30
Occupation	Working women	62	31
	House wife	45	22.5
	Student	93	46.5
Income per Month	Below 10000	32	16
	10000-20000	97	48.5
	Above 20000	71	35.5
Reason for Preferring Brand	Easy to handle	46	23
	Convenience	81	40.5
	Smooth running	41	20.5
	Others	32	16
Media Preference	Television	36	18
	News paper	64	32
	Internet	55	27.5
	Others	45	22.5
Mode of Payment	Cash	95	47.5
	Credit	105	52.5

Interpretation: Out of 200 respondents 75 belongs to 10-20 age group. If we observe the marital status of the respondents 140 of them belongs to single category. The occupation with 46.5 belongs to student category and 31% belongs to working women category. About 48.5% of the respondents drop under 10K-20 K income categories. Majority of the respondents prefer two wheeler brands because of its convenience of usage. Easy handling is the second priority. And 32% prefer news paper as the media to get information. And mostly prefer credit payment option for the purchase of the product.

Table 2: Preference of Brand

S.No	Brand	Respondents	Percentage
1	Scooty pep	17	8.5
2	Honda Activa	32	16
3	Pleasure	13	6.5
4	Honda Dio	25	12.5
5	Vespa	29	14.5
6	TVS Wego	18	9
7	Suzuki Access	50	25
8	Others	16	8

Chart 1:

Interpretation: The above chart reveal that 25% of women consumers prefer Suzuki access two wheeler. Secondly they prefer Activa vehicle around 16% out of 200 respondents. Then the third position vested in the hands of Vespa that around 15%. And least of them prefer pleasure vehicle around only 6%.

Table 3: Factors influenced to buy two wheeler

S.No	Factors	Respondents	Percentage
1	Price	60	30
2	Good mileage	23	11.5
3	Better look & style	11	5.5
4	Value for money	15	7.5
5	After sales service	12	6
6	Reputed Brand	24	12
7	Pickup and speed	13	6.5
8	New models	21	10.5
9	Easy maintenance	20	10
10	Others	1	.5

Chart 2:

Interpretation: The above chart reveals that Price is the major factor of buying decision (30%). Brand is the second factor which influence the buying decision among women consumers. Mileage, New models, Easy maintenance etc are the rest of the factors which influence buying decision.

Z Test:

To test the growth in buying decision of two wheeler among women consumers.

H0: There is no significant difference in the growth in the buying decision of two wheeler among women consumers.

Table 3: Z test of growth in buying decision among women consumers.

S.No	Time period	No. of Respondents
1	0-1 year	18
2	1 – 2 years	35
3	2 – 3 years	85
4	More than 3 year	62
	Total	200

$$Z = \frac{X - \mu}{S.E}$$

Calculation of μ :

Table 3.1

Time period	No. of Respondents	X – d	d ²
0-1 year	18	-32	1024
1-2 years	35	-15	225
2-3 years	85	35	1225
More than 3 years	62	12	144
Total	200		2618

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SD} &= \frac{\sqrt{2618}}{4} \\ &= 25.583 \\ \text{SE} &= \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}} \\ &= \frac{25.583}{\sqrt{200}} \\ &= 1.809 \\ \text{Z} &= \frac{50 - 25.583}{1.809} \\ &= 13.497 \end{aligned}$$

The table value of Z at 0.05 level of significance is 1.645. Here, the calculated value (13.497) is greater than the table value. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0). And accept the alternative hypothesis.

Hence, There is no significant difference in the growth in the buying decision of two wheeler among women consumers

Findings:

- ✓ Out of 200 respondents, 37.5% of them were among the age of 10-20 years.
- ✓ Marital status is comes around 70% of total respondents.
- ✓ Majority of respondents comes under students category
- ✓ Majorities monthly Income between Rs.10000 – Rs.20000
- ✓ Most of them prefer two wheeler because of its Convenience.
- ✓ Majority of them prefer News paper media to get awareness.
- ✓ Majority of them prefer Credit mode of payment
- ✓ There is no significant growth in the buying decision of two wheeler among Women Consumers in Calicut City
- ✓ Majority of the respondents says that Price is the main factor which influence Buying Decision

Conclusion:

This study focused on the Women preference towards two wheeler brands in Calicut City. The study pointed out that women possess two wheelers for their convenience. This study has observed many factors that affect women buying behaviour. At the time of purchasing two wheeler women has different choice for two wheelers but the purchase decision depends on various factors like product attributes, price, credit facility and brand. Study concluded that Suzuki Access is the leading brand of two wheeler in Calicut city followed by Honda and Vespa. This study helped the researcher to use theoretical knowledge and to gain useful insights about the importance of women perception.

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